

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

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**STEECCI Social Innovation Labs –
Methodology & Handbook**

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D5.1 – STECCI SOCIAL INNOVATION LABS – METHODOLOGY & HANDBOOK

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Description of the related task and the deliverable

Task 5.1 *Community-based impact strategies for a sustainable stećci ecosystem (M2–7)* develops a robust methodology and handbook with a selection of methods for stakeholder engagement, collaborative knowledge production and co-creation for the three STECCI Social Innovation Labs (BIH, HR, ME) and two citizen science pilots on stećci and limestone tombstones in general (SRB, DE). The aim is to enable solutions to overcome social challenges by taking advantage of the rich and unique cultural heritage (CH) of stećci in all partner regions.

Pursuing a community-empowering and multi-stakeholder-sourced engagement strategy, five tailor-made engagement concepts for the sustainable and socially inclusive CH valorisation are presented in deliverable 5.1 *STECCI Social Innovation Labs – Methodology & Handbook*. The document provides guidance and sets the scene for the lab activities in the follow-up task 5.2 collaboratively working on the socially inclusive valorisation building opportunities for social innovation and the sensitive exploitation of stećci in the context of cultural tourism.

STECCI Consortium

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ABBREVIATIONS

AR	Augmented Reality
BIH	Bosnia and Herzegovina
CC	Climate change
CCI	Cultural and creative industries
CH	Cultural heritage
CoC	Code of Conduct
CS	Citizen science
CSO	Civil society organisations
D	Deliverable
DE	Germany
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HR	Croatia
ICOMOS	International Council on Monuments and Sites
KPI	Key performance indicator
ME	Montenegro
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
NPO	Non-profit organisation
QH	Quadruple helix
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SI	Social innovation
SL	Social lab
SRB	Serbia
STH	Stakeholder
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of this project is to develop and implement new, sustainable strategies for the long-term preservation of cultural heritage. D5.1 *STECCI Social Innovation Labs – Methodology & Handbook* provides strategies and methods to build alliances with different audiences or stakeholder (STH) groups as a precondition to integrate cultural heritage into development and planning processes, empowering communities, building capacity, strengthening the cultural heritage sector, harnessing digital technologies, improving evidence-based reporting and diversifying funding sources.

In view of the drastic effects of climate change, the preservation of cultural heritage is the focus of a holistic approach that involves a wide range of stakeholders such as scientists, restorers, citizens, the cultural creative industries and decisionmakers in the policy sphere.

D5.1 presents an agile framework and tailor-made concept for STECCI Social Innovation Labs enabling the co-creation of, among others, the capacity building program and the building of sustainable cultural tourism strategies that can be implemented across “stećci regions”. The arts and the cultural and creative industries (CCI) are addressed as important drivers for the community well-being, the regeneration of mostly remote stećci places, the economic growth, and the protection of cultural heritage in times of rapid climate change.

This deliverable is part of Work Package 5 that focuses on the active engagement of stakeholders from quadruple helix for the preservation of cultural heritage and the development of sustainable strategies for cultural tourism. It aims to involve multi-stakeholders from different sectors such as civil society, industry, academia, and politics to promote social, cultural and economic developments in the target regions. The social lab methodology is adapted to enable transdisciplinary experiments where local stakeholders, practitioners and researchers work together to address complex social challenges and generate social innovations.

D5.1 provides a bundle of 14 creative, interactive, reflective, or evidence-gathering methods to foster pilot activities. All activities follow the rationale on how local communities can benefit from cultural heritage, the role of citizen science in deepening people's relationship with stećci and how participatory approaches can promote the strengthening of place meanings.

The involvement of citizens, especially young people and children, and the collaboration with the cultural and creative industries should increase citizens' scientific literacy and raise awareness of sustainable impacts which will be outlined in the final policy brief for sustainable stećci tourism at later stage of the project.

1. INTRODUCTION

The STECCI project builds on a holistic approach to cultural heritage (CH), and the idea of CH as a potential driver and enabler of sustainable developments. In this context, CH can be defined as a vessel for creativity and social innovation.

Stećci are regionally distinctive medieval necropoles that date from the 12th to 16th centuries CE. Artefacts are in about 28 sites across Bosnia and Herzegovina, western Serbia, western Montenegro, and central and southern Croatia. All sites represent cemeteries inscribed on the *World Heritage List* since 2016 (UNESCO World Heritage Convention).

One major project pillar is the safeguarding of these artefacts linked to the appropriate preservation in times of climate change. The other pillar fosters stećci in the context of the social landscape. Using a place-based and community-focused approach highlights a social layer like addressed in the *Australia ICOMOS Burra Charter* (2013). The charter introduces heritage places, emphasizing community values and primarily including places that hold significance due to their association with certain events rather than physical evidence. A similar scope, which can be also defined as a living and dynamic ecosystem, was taken by the key international conservation guideline, the *European Landscape Convention* (2004) characterizing landscape as an area perceived by people and an outcome that results from action and interaction of natural and/or human factors.

Following these considerations, stećci can be understood as a phenomenon with the potential to contribute to the societal and social layer of each region and beyond. Facing a unique and site-specific legacy, the balance between a sustainable valorisation of these local resources and community well-being is one major challenge to be addressed in the STECCI labs. The approach puts stakeholder needs into the centre of its endeavours by asking: **How can the local community benefit from cultural heritage?** Engaging local stakeholders is expected to generate innovative ways to safeguard, valorise and manage CH, as well as to promote the replication and scalability of the stakeholder or citizen engagement strategies and activities (see Commission Recommendation (EU) 2024/736).

D5.1 focuses on community-based impact strategies for a “sustainable stećci ecosystem” (M2–7) and sets the scene for a stakeholder engagement involving communities that are interested in being better informed and involved in participatory activities, as well as tourism planning processes and participatory heritage management models.

Further overarching questions raised in the participatory research and co-creation are: Does participation in place-based citizen science play a role in connecting people more deeply to stećci cultural heritage? In what ways do participatory approaches such as social (innovation) labs and place-based citizen science encourage the strengthening and the valorisation of CH places? How can awareness-raising help better

embed CH in innovation ecosystems? And how to inform the design of sustainable cultural tourism in planning and policies?

In this context, D5.1 suggests practical steps for engaging core stakeholders to become contributors in the CH research and the co-creation of a tailor-made valorisation strategy that prioritizes the promotion of social inclusion, the improvement of well-being of communities, as well as boosts capacities of stakeholders and organisations working with stećci. To do so, STECCI project focuses on the empowerment of local communities. Values and a shared emotional connection that residents ascribe to their public heritage are of importance for the sustainable development of a community of interest and new cultural services based on tradition, local history, and current needs.

A range of participatory methods, tools and integrative approaches are designed and implemented by the four STECCI pilot partner countries; the “non- stećci” pilot in Germany shares this mission for sensitive valorisation of cultural heritage. In all pilots, STECCI stakeholder engagement strategy intends to support placemaking as an approach to mutual and cross-border learning, and works towards innovative forms of socially inclusive planning, design, and management of public or institutional spaces. Transdisciplinary activities are expected to contribute to a new perspective on dealing with stećci heritage sites – building on the connection between people and the places as fundamental part of a CH protection plan. Placemaking can be defined as making sense of a place in the views of stakeholders’ vision, strategies, and practices (i.e. Habibah et al. 2013, Akbar & Edelenbos 2021). From the community or residents’ perspective, placemaking can be described as a process of adding value and meaning to the public realm through community-based research and revitalization projects rooted in local values history, culture, and the natural environment. Placemaking is also a component of participation in community-planning bringing different interests together through the integration of various stakeholders’ viewpoints and functions. Such a dynamic approach can be applied to re-define pristine spaces (i.e. Iwinska 2017) surrounding the stećci necropolises.

According to some studies on the social and economic value of CH, “(...) Heritage, if properly managed, can be instrumental in enhancing social inclusion, developing intercultural dialogue, shaping the identity of a territory, improving the quality of the environment, providing social cohesion, and – on the economic side – stimulating tourism development, creating jobs and enhancing the investment climate” (Dümcke & Gnedovsky 2013).

Moreover, the unique artefacts of stećci necropolises can be a catalyst for cooperation (or conflict) and social innovation. Potential areas of social and socio-economic innovation are, e.g. the promotion of local heritage as a pole of attraction for visitors; the utilization of local knowledge for the conservation of cultural diversity; the development of new and innovative service (or product) ideas with a transformative potential; an update of regulations and legal provisions; the initiation of new networks for local collaboration and cooperation; or greater openness to community participation and democratic dialogue (Panagiotopoulos et. al 2023).

STECCI WP5 (*Community-based impact strategies for sustainable stećci ecosystem*) addresses three main areas with the help of a people-centered and community-based approach to build a socially inclusive research and valorisation strategy. Based on stakeholder feedback, the consortium creates (1) a tailor-made capacity building program and (2) enables peer learning for a smart cultural management and conservation; moreover, (3) it analyses how to overcome the remoteness of most of the stećci sites with a focus on a sustainable cultural tourism strategy.

Fig. 1: Community building and participation in STECCI

D5.1 (*STECCI Social Innovation Labs – Methodology & Handbook*) is structured in three main parts. The parts are as follows: 1) literature analysis, 2) introduction to the STECCI stakeholder engagement strategy based on a mapping that will be updated at least at three points during the project, and 3) a set of methods to build a social lab for collaborative knowledge production and co-creation. The handbook mirrors the initial phase of WP5 and gives orientation for the follow-up task T5.2 (*Bringing STECCI labs to life*, M8-21) in which the test of tailor-made approaches is foreseen. Afterwards, results will source the implementation of T5.3 (*Building capacities for stećci stakeholders*). Furthermore, the document links activities in WP5 with WP4 and prepares the co-creation setting for T4.4. (*Virtual tours*, M4-36) and then, later, for T4.2. (*Educational Game Development*, M19-26).

Fig. 2: Interdependencies of T5.1 and T5.2

2. LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Due to the nature of the STECCI project, an interdisciplinary scope in the research must be applied. The first step involves a critical discourse analysis of literature including monographs, peer-reviewed articles, white papers, guidelines, project reports, scientific papers, manuals and policy documents from the previous six years (Y=2018 to 2024). Its aim is to position the understanding and approach to cultural heritage in our pilot countries and to build a theoretical framework for the field research with a focus on sensitive valorisation of cultural heritage. Another focus is on case studies dealing with selected cases from the STECCI pilot countries with customized solutions.

Fig. 3: Overview of literature analysis process

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

For the literature review the following questions were asked to identify key words:

- How can local stakeholders benefit from cultural heritage?
- Can place-based citizen science contribute to the improvement of deeper cohesion between people and CH?
- How do participatory approaches strengthen and valorize the significance of sites?
- How to raise awareness for stećci CH in the local, regional, and transregional ecosystems?
- And to what extent can stećci be used to strengthen and promote sustainable cultural tourism?

With these questions in mind, four main topics were identified to refine the required search results: a) “CH & Impact”, b) “CH & Peacemaking”, c) “CH & Co-Creation”, and d) “CH & Stakeholder Engagement”. In a

joint co-brainstorming process with consortium partners, keywords relevant to the literature analysis were defined for these four subjects.

Fig. 4: Major topics to the keywords of the STECCI literature search

TOPIC	KEYWORDS
<p>CH & CO-CREATION</p>	<p>collaborative creativity, collaborative planning and/or decision-making, community-led initiatives, cross-sector partnerships, cultural route, decent work and economic growth, digital skills, industry, innovation and infrastructure, international cooperation, local communities’ entrepreneurship, multi-stakeholder collaboration, participatory design, social capital, stakeholder involvement, sustainable communication, user-driven innovation</p>
<p>CH & IMPACT</p>	<p>assessment metrics, citizen science, climate change, climate neutrality, climate resilience, cultural literacy, cultural tourism, digitization, environmental conservation, fusion of art & technology, green practices, integrative or holistic approaches, intersecting fields, measuring social impact, outcome evaluation, pace-making, preservation, responsible consumption and production, smart cultural management, smart management of cultural heritage, social and economic sustainability, social entrepreneurship, social innovation, social return on investment (SROI), social value, sustainability, sustainable cities and communities, sustainable development, sustainable heritage management, sustainable heritage management</p>
<p>CH & PEACEMAKING</p>	<p>conflict resolution, conflict-sensitive climate policies, contested sites, cultural identity, ethnic and religious tolerance, peace and justice, peace education, quality education, resilience, security, social cohesion, strong institutions</p>
<p>CH & STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT</p>	<p>accessibility, branding, climate action, community engagement, community-led innovation, cross-sectoral challenges, diversity, educational programs, empowerment, equity, gender equality, heritage education, inclusion, inclusive community development, leadership opportunities, outreach initiatives, public awareness campaigns, reduced inequality, representation, resilience, strong institutions</p>

Tab. 1: Keywords for STECCI literature analysis

After identifying this list of keywords, an initial search was conducted at supranational and European level, focusing on international organisations and their publications on this topic. A further search on the "Web of Science" platform was carried out by country or region (BIH, HR, DE, ME, and SRB) and focused on the publication years 2018 – 2023.

The first search on Web of Science result yielded over 200,000 publications. It was specified that the term "cultural heritage" must be included, paired with another keyword from the list and the publication language must be English. This ultimately led to 667 results. The literature was downloaded as an excel file for further processing. This file also contains the abstracts of the results.

A second search using only the search term "stecak" and variations of this term such as "stecci" and "stecak", as well as "necropolis" and "sites", as well as the countries of the pilots revealed a result of 31,134 publications. Here, too, only results from the years 2018–2023 were taken into consideration. The keyword "cultural heritage" was also included as an urgent keyword, which reduced the results to 135. The second search for "stecak" looked for articles containing "peacemaking", which produced only one result. If "conservation" was used instead, there were 28 results.

2.2 RESULTS

The identified literature discusses the impact of climate change on urban cultural heritage, including energy efficiency, risk mapping, preservation, stakeholder involvement and sustainable development. It also addresses the challenges and opportunities for preserving and managing cultural heritage in the face of climate change. The literature emphasizes the importance of considering climate change in the management, preservation of cultural heritage and the economic resilience of the pilot countries regarding cultural heritage sites.

When analysing the existing literature, it became clear that although there is a great interest in cultural heritage and history on the part of the natural sciences, as well as archaeology, environmental sciences, and tourism, little can be found regarding cultural policy. Most citations linked to meso-level were made regarding the topics "hospitality, leisure, sport & tourism", then followed by "archaeometry" and "forestry" (Fig. 5). Topics cited at the micro-level highlighted the importance of the tourism sector (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5: Literature citation linked to meso topics

Fig. 6: Literature citation linked to micro topics

A further filter was applied only on publications from the year 2023 to be able to use the most recent results for the analysis. This led to a total of 73 results. Literature that did not fit could be excluded with the help of an initial review of the abstracts. The literature found was re-checked regarding relevance to the project and to WP5.

For further analysis, the first 667 articles identified were sorted according to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The following SDGs, in order of relevance to the project, were chosen to be relevant for WP5:

- 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities
- 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions
- 04: Quality Education
- 05: Gender Equality

The resulting 240 publications are presented as follows in figure 7. In a next step, the SDG-related search was combined with the keywords "stećak" and "cultural heritage" and resulted in 58 publications presented in figure 8.

Fig. 7: Classification of literature according to SDG

Fig. 8: Classification to SDG, stećak, CH

As can be seen from both analyses regarding the breakdown of SDG topics, most publications deal with the SDG "Sustainable Cities and Communities", followed by "Quality Education" and then a small amount with "Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions" and "Gender Equality". This indicates that in recent years research in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Serbia, Montenegro, and Germany prioritized the topic of "cultural heritage" in context and connection with sustainability, environmental protection, and climate change.

The consortium partners were also asked to identify regional literature based on our search parameters and were able to contribute literature and papers, some of which would have been impossible to identify outside of the STECCI project due to the language barrier (all non-English literature). Over 100 references were generated, providing a comprehensive assessment framework for the impact of CH, and exploring the link between cultural heritage, education, and sustainable development. Various aspects of CH are explored in the identified sources, including specific sites, historical context, and documentation efforts. The focus is on the documentation and preservation of sites, art, and cultural heritage in specific regions, with an emphasis on historical and aesthetic aspects.

Based on the literature, it can be summarized that cultural heritage contributes to the quality of life in small and medium-sized towns. However, the preservation and use of CH depends on specific conditions and depends on context (Knoop et al. 2023). In some regions, school textbooks only make a limited contribution to strengthening national identity (Vasilijevic & Semiz 2023). There is a need for a more balanced presentation of cultural heritage. Here, the valuation of ecosystem-services-assessments enables better integration of cultural heritage into regional planning and policy making. The valuation of services shows that the preservation of cultural heritage can improve the quality of life in border regions (Correa et al. 2023).

However, anthropology and critical heritage studies also share a negative view of the role of bureaucracy in heritage management in post-conflict regions. Field research suggests that the process of "bureaucratizing" collective identities according to UNESCO principles is more promising than purely political or purely academic approaches. The preservation of intangible and tangible cultural heritage has proven to be an effective tool for deflecting identity conflicts (Milenkovic 2023). The administration and management of cultural heritage has shifted from being the sole responsibility of the state to partnership-based approaches. The analysis of public-civil, public-private, and public-private-municipal partnerships shows advantages and disadvantages, with public-private partnerships being the best represented. Local initiatives can use these partnerships to promote sustainable development (Zuvela et al. 2023).

The literature found will further serve to better understand the complex history and diverse religious and ethnic influences of the Balkan region, which is rich in CH (Hajzeri 2022, Ljustina 2019). This heritage, which includes necropoles, is often used as a tool for political and territorial claims leading to challenges in its management and preservation (Galaty 2011). Conflicting narratives about the region's cultural heritage further complicate these issues. Despite these challenges, the region's cultural heritage has the potential to foster cooperation and understanding between different countries (Hajzeri 2022, Tomka 2014).

3. STECCI STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT FOR SENSITIVE VALORISATION

This section provides information on the methodology behind the activities carried out in T5.1. It is related to the mapping of current and potential stakeholders aiming to establish a multi-stakeholder group in each of the five regional pilots, and then to build a community of interest to enable cross-border peer learning. This community of interest is intended to provide a platform for new partnerships between institutions and further STECCI stakeholders with high impact and influence.

The stakeholder engagement in STECCI is a continuous, voluntary activity providing an open and active dialogue between diverse stakeholder groups. STECCI takes advantage of the so-called quadruple helix (HQ) concept (Carayannis and Campbell, 2009; 2012; 2014). The concept invites stakeholders from science and research, industry and business, policymaking, and civil society to participate in the interventions of the three STECCI SI labs. Lab participants become a reflexive working group collaborating with the STECCI consortium. STECCI labs form (T5.2) a community of interest that can bring different interests at stake – one example is the STECCI representation in festivals, the STECCI summer schools and the dialogue events with policymakers and influencers. This engagement also contributes to the results and guidance documents such as the policy brief. Due to the specifics of the pilots, the stakeholder involvement has different compositions of stakeholder groups including

- vulnerable groups such as children or seniors,
- civil society organisations (CSO),
- key-knowledge holders and multipliers from the local community,
- non-governmental organisations (NGO) in cultural heritage and education,
- representatives from tourism sector,
- policymakers or influencers,
- academic researchers, mainly in an early career phase, and
- artists and cultural and creative workers, educators.

A preliminary composition of stakeholders of each pilot is presented in chapter 3.3 describing use cases and the initial engagement strategies.

3.1 STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

The stakeholder mapping consists of three steps that include the identification, the analysis and the engagement of stakeholders following an iterative process.

The first two steps include exploratory interviews using scout questions and brainstorming meetings with pilot lead partners using their regional knowledge and local networks to make a profile of the appropriate stakeholder maps and databases. The focus is on project outcomes and important key knowledge holders and further stakeholders.

Fig. 9: Three steps of stakeholder mapping

Stakeholder engagement is a crucial aspect of stakeholder mapping as it ensures that the project meets the needs and expectations of the user and other parties involved or concerned.

- **STAKEHOLDER**

Person or organisation with influence on and an interest or concern related to the project and its objectives and represent all QH groups. These stakeholders are relevant for STECCI labs and citizen science activities.

- **USER**

Person, who uses the findings and results of project. Users are relevant for the STECCI labs.

The various stakeholder groups were determined in a joint brainstorming process.

Fig. 10: Major categories of the STECCI stakeholder mapping

There are essentially five levels of engagement with stakeholders: information, consultation, involvement, collaboration, and user. These levels correspond to numbers 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 that are given as options in the engagement level column in the STECCI stakeholder database template.

1. Information: This stakeholder group is identified to be at the minimum level of engagement. Communication is mostly one-way, stakeholder input is not actively sought; however, transparency and awareness are important.

Stakeholders at the informing level show low to moderate interest and have a low level of influence, with limited or no direct influence on the decision-making process.

2. Consultation: Stakeholder's feedback, opinions, and suggestions is actively obtained. It goes beyond simply informing stakeholders and provides an opportunity for them to express their views. Stakeholders are asked for their input, and their perspectives are considered in the decision-making process.

These stakeholders present a moderate to high interest in our project, however, a low to moderate influence.

3. Involvement: Stakeholders take engagement a step further by actively involving them in the decision-making process. These stakeholders have a high level of interest and a moderate to high level of influence on our project. Therefore, they are seen as partners rather than mere recipients of information and are given the opportunity to provide input and influence the outcome.

In this level of stakeholder engagement, stakeholders have valuable knowledge, experiences, and perspectives that can significantly enhance the project's outcomes.

4. Collaboration: The collaboration process involves stakeholders with high levels of interest, commitment, and influence in our project.

At this stage, stakeholders are active partners in decision-making and their input is given equal weight alongside other factors. That means they can participate in shaping the project or decision and share a sense of ownership - so we must treat them as part of our team.

5. The last level of engagement level, the **users** are the affected category of people on whom the results of the project will apply directly. Users might be persons that have not contributed or collaborated in the project yet but are the user of the project output.

The groups 4 and 5 are expected to have a high intrinsic motivation to become participants of the STECCI labs.

Fig. 11: Engagement levels of stakeholders

The previous tool to the stakeholder identification is a list of scout questions, which is constantly revised and used in the exploratory interviews and collaborative brainstorming sessions with pilot leaders. The questions comprised a context analysis requesting the geographical, historic, and socio-cultural “DNA” of the pilot, the specific objectives of the pilot lab and the foreseen co-creation activities. It addresses questions of social inclusion and supports the joint vision-building for sustainable results. Furthermore, it looks at organisational aspects, roles, and responsibilities in the pilot labs (appendix).

Fig. 12: Steps of stakeholder mapping

In parallel, a list of stakeholder groups is established collected from consortium partners involved in T2.1. In the next step the potential involvement is analysed, again together with all pilots prioritizing the expected engagement level of listed stakeholders, asking about the likely persons to engage in the activities and events of the labs due to their interests and their potential impact or influence on the project. This information is used to kick-off the invitation process for the STECCI SI labs and further pilots. The following table

indicates the total number of every stakeholder group linked to the three pilots. The database will be iteratively updated: the next step will be taken during the kick-off event of the STECCI labs implementing a stakeholder and needs assessment together with the participants.

PARTNER STH GROUP	UNSA	UDG	UMAS	SPK	UNSPMF
	PUBLIC SECTOR	3	12	2	6
IDENTIFIED USER	2	5	1	1	1
HIGHER EDUCATION & RESEARCH	4	3	2	2	1
IDENTIFIED USER	3	---	---	---	1
GENERAL EDUCATION	3	---	2	2	6
IDENTIFIED USER	---	---	1	2	5
TOURISM	2	2	3	---	3
IDENTIFIED USER	---	---	---	---	---
MEDIA	2	2	---	---	4
IDENTIFIED USER	---	---	---	---	---
CULTURAL & CREATIVE INDUSTRY	8	4	10	1	1
IDENTIFIED USER	---	2	2	---	---
3rd SECTOR	1	3	2	---	1
IDENTIFIED USER	---	---	---	---	---
OTHER	4	1	---	1	---
IDENTIFIED USER	---	---	---	---	---
TOTAL NUMBER	27	27	21	12	19

Tab. 2: Stakeholder mapping overview per pilot

In addition, task leader implements research on organisations at a supra-national level. Partners complement with a further identification on the national and regional level. Updates will be done at two points in the project timeline – during T5.2 and T5.3 subsequently.

The explorative approach is also applied to refine the qualitative case study of the preparatory phase, including interviews with at least four local or regional stakeholders representing social or creative entrepreneurs, artists, CSOs or non-profit organisations (NPOs), the municipality, policymakers, tourism organisations and residents of the neighbourhood during the kick-off phase of the social labs. The interview partners are identified through the initial stakeholder mapping and then snowballing method.

The following table presents the general scheme including criteria to filter stakeholders for the mapping.

CATEGORIES	INFORMATION
PILOTS	Assignment to which pilot
TERRITORIAL SCALE	Classification of the relevance of stakeholders at scale: community / municipality / region / trans-region / European level
SECTOR	Classification of the stakeholders' fields of activity: public sector / higher education & research / general education / tourism / media / cultural & creative industries / 3 rd sector / other
ORGANISATION TYPE	According to the quadruple helix approach for the development of social, needs-oriented, and community-driven innovations, the following types of organisations can be selected: association / cooperative / NGO / community representative / entrepreneur / public authorities / private company / other
NAME ORGANISATION	Full name of the stakeholder
CONTACT PERSON SURNAME	Surname of the main contact person at the selected stakeholder
NAME	Name of the main contact person at the selected stakeholder
TITLE	Title of the main contact person: DR / MD / MR / MRS / MS / PhD / PROF. DR / TBD / [nothing]
GENDER	Gender of the main contact person: FEMALE / MALE / NON-BINARY / NA.
FUNCTION	Function of the main contact person within the organisation
EMAIL	The e-mail of the main contact person, in some cases generally for an entire organisation
RELEVANCE TO THE OBJECTIVES	Relation of the organisation to the STECCI project - multiple answers are possible: O1-CO-CREATION OF A RESEARCH STRATEGY O2-CAPACITY BUILDING PROGRAMS O3-OVERCOMING REMOTENESS OF STECCI LABS
GENERAL INFO	Further and general notes on the stakeholder and/or organisation
ENGAGEMENT LEVEL	Commitment level of the stakeholder/organisation from 1 (not much) to 5 (user); users benefit directly from the results and measures of the STECCI project.

Tab. 3: Categories for STECCI stakeholder database and contact list

3.2 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

The STECCI engagement strategy reflects the main aspects and approaches enabling project partners to create hands-on plans for engagement. Strategy aims to establish and maintain open, inclusive, participatory processes throughout the project. The work with multi-stakeholder groups is also expected to bring together relevant stakeholders having a stake in the policy challenges addressed by STECCI; specifically, the protection, the valorisation, the management of the stećci stones for the local level of each pilot and beyond. The multi-stakeholder groups can interact with the international partners from STECCI during different events, while consortium partners act as moderators or facilitators of local processes, and as trainers during the summer schools. The initial strategic engagement approach includes three major benefits or areas:

1) **Learning and awareness-raising:** Involving stakeholders in the project can help to raise awareness of the goals of STECCI. Identifying stakeholders also provides an audience for the subsequent dissemination of project outputs. Further, STECCI has an important role to play in raising awareness of stakeholders concerning the potential impacts of climate change in the related territories and regions, and the types of CH preservation response that are available to address these impacts.

2) **Enhancing legitimacy:** STECCI is also focused on raising adaptive capacity around the response to climate change impacts to STECCI. All research activities and experiments will provide a blueprint to other stećci cultural heritage sites. By involving stakeholders during the development of the blueprint, its legitimacy as a valuable document to help guide decision-making will be enhanced by helping to create an output that more closely meets the needs of its users. Increasing the transparency of the processes leading to the creation of the STECCI blueprint is also important in this respect. This will also encourage the blueprint to have a life beyond STECCI through encouraging ownership and the later uptake of project outcomes. Community participation is an essential issue in the context of STECCI heritage management and will be focused on too.

3) **Information provision:** This relates principally to disseminating information concerning stećci in general, the key outputs of the project, which will include reports and publications relating to climate change and resilience. This will take place principally through lab workshops and further events such as a festival, a conference, or guidance documents.

Suggestions on site-specific topics and how to set up stakeholder engagement activities are initially described in the following case studies per pilot lab or demo site with citizen science activities, respectively. Due to the iterative nature of the project, use cases and strategies will be updated.

3.3 STAKEHOLDER MAPPING IN THE CONTEXT OF STECCI PILOTS

For a better understanding of the individual pilots and the sites, a thorough analysis of the respective locations and their circumstances is necessary. This section briefly introduces the three pilots in Bosnia & Herzegovina, Montenegro, and Croatia, as well as the two sites in Germany and Serbia. In addition to the

geographical location and accessibility, the historical and cultural significance of the sites is also highlighted. This overview – described as the DNA of the places – is crucial for an appropriate classification of places, monuments, and sites.

Furthermore, expected challenges and risks are listed to design the action plans of the pilots. In addition, the primary (due to GA) and complementary objectives with a focus on the social layer (co-designed with partners in brainstorming sessions) of pilots are also briefly listed.

Furthermore, the vulnerable and marginalised groups in pilots, as well as planned mechanisms and synergies to engage these groups are identified. Finally, the vision of pilot partners and expected results of intended measures are briefly presented to define a reference figure for later assessment of achievements.

3.3.1 BOSNIA & HERZEGOVINA

Pilot Case	Population	Main & complementary objectives
Križeviči (municipality Olovo)	Križeviči → 176 Olovo → 10,175	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - condition assessment and in-situ conservation - promoting the significance of CH - sustainable tourism
Kopošići (municipality Ilijaš)	19,603 (2013) Currently there are no residents in the Kopošići village	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sustainable development of local communities through the development of cultural tourism, creation, and sale of handicrafts linked to the concept of stećci - connecting through common cultural heritage

Geographic and historic context and cultural DNA of the sites

The uninhabited village of Kopošići in the municipality of Ilijaš hosts a stećak necropolis adjacent to the Catholic cemetery, containing an epitaph mentioning Prince Batić's burial, yet the site has significantly deteriorated due to neglect stemming from the abandonment of nearby residential areas; furthermore, situated northwest of Sarajevo, within the municipality of Ilijaš, the region showcases diverse topography and mineral-rich locations, notably including the medieval Dubrovnik Fortress, designated a national monument in 2003 and undergoing current restoration efforts.

Križeviči, situated in the western part of the municipality of Olovo in the Zenica-Doboj canton, has a population of just under 200 spread over 3.42 KM², encompassing settlements like Križeviči, Meorača, Boganovići, and Mogušë, despite an estimated 280 inhabitants in 119 households. However, despite its rich cultural and historical heritage, including three stećak necropoles, the region lacks sufficient protection, infrastructure development, and promotion, even though stećaks are depicted on the 10 KM banknote of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Moreover, the municipality of Olovo, positioned strategically 56 KM from Sarajevo and 75 KM from Tuzla, boasts a long history dating back to the 14th century, marked by economic prosperity

driven by lead ore mining and trade, as evidenced by landmarks like the Monastery of the Holy Virgin and its enduring cultural heritage.

Major issues

Identified challenges include limited accessibility, inadequate accommodation, insufficient public transportation, adverse weather conditions, concerns about private ownership, and the absence of established tourist routes.

Objectives

The main objective is to assess and conserve stećci sites, focusing on educating young researchers, conservators, and citizens about their importance, while complementary objectives include strengthening tourism, promoting economic growth, and preserving cultural heritage. This involves educating citizens, students and heritage visitors about extreme climate events and monitoring conditions in stećci to raise awareness of climate change effects, as well as increasing the value of cultural heritage, promoting cultural tourism and enhancing the local economy. Additionally, the project aims to frame stećci as a transnational heritage promoting international cooperation and social inclusion, particularly by engaging older residents in small settlements and raising awareness among young people for a sustainable future.

Stakeholder mapping

The stakeholders involved in the project encompass a broad spectrum with representatives from the public sector, cultural and creative industry, media, general and higher education, and tourism. The cooperation with a variety of interest groups enables the broadest possible and most dynamic interdisciplinary collaboration. It also promotes partnerships with the municipalities and facilitates access to knowledge and information.

UNSA has currently identified 27 stakeholders and five users.

Vulnerable groups

The mechanism for elderly inclusion involves integrating wool crafts into the cultural narrative of STECCI through the "Zlatne ruke" group, while for children with disabilities, it entails providing adaptive tools and materials to facilitate their active participation in STECCI-related activities. Both groups will benefit from tailored workshops and focus groups aimed at engaging them effectively and understanding their unique perspectives and needs, with additional project materials provided in various formats to encourage the participation of people with disabilities, ultimately aiming to promote their inclusion and meaningful involvement in the STECCI project.

Mechanism and synergies for social inclusion

Various associations in the municipality of Ilijaš prioritize assisting vulnerable groups, yet inadequate transportation infrastructure poses challenges for their access to stećak necropolises, necessitating alternative approaches like thematic workshops. Collaboration with municipalities like Ilijaš/Olovo could offer suitable venues for project activities, particularly targeting schoolchildren, to foster cultural heritage appreciation. Proposed activities encompass mobile workshops, craft sessions with local artisans, interactive storytelling, small exhibitions, and educational workshops tailored to vulnerable groups, aiming to enhance accessibility to the cultural-historical experience of stećci despite transportation obstacles.

Expected outcome of pilot activities

The pilot project aims to holistically manage cultural heritage by integrating preservation, climate resilience, and sustainable tourism to establish the municipality as a model for comprehensive preservation and revitalization of stećci's cultural significance to foster local identity and community pride. Economically, the project promotes cultural tourism, generates income for local communities and enhances ecological resilience through climate atlas and conservation strategies, while citizen engagement in climate-related data collection raises awareness and influences policies at local and national levels, fostering cultural responsibility, aiding policy development, and contributing to socio-economic development. Youth involvement will promote civic and environmental responsibility and position the municipality as a leader in heritage conservation, ultimately strengthening cultural harmony, educational opportunities, community empowerment, regional cooperation, peacebuilding efforts, as well as promoting a shared understanding of cultural preservation.

Accessibility

Access to the Kopošići necropolis involves traversing a partially asphalted road, initially leading to the Misoča quarry, and then transitioning to a narrow macadam road. This latter part of the journey, extending towards the medieval city of Dubrovnik and the necropolis itself, is characterized by numerous narrowings, curves, and passages through forested areas.

Accessing the Križevići necropolis in the Olovo municipality is primarily facilitated by a well-maintained route. Travelers from Sarajevo can utilize public transportation options to reach Olovo throughout the workweek, with Centrotrans Bus Booking providing detailed information on bus lines and schedules. From Olovo, a regular bus line departs every weekday for Križevići. The journey involves a scenic 20–30-minute walk from Olovo to Križevići, with the path occasionally steep but generally navigable, passing through a local village. However, these localities are not suitable for people with disabilities or the elderly due to the need for extensive walking caused by poor road infrastructure. There is no dedicated cycling or hiking routes to the necropolises, though small pathways nearby exist, albeit not directly leading to the sites and typically not cleared in winter.

3.3.2 MONTENEGRO

Pilot Case	Population	Main & complementary objectives
Žabljak	2,000 (2003)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sustainable tourism - clarifying the importance of CH
Pluzine	1,400 (2003)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improvement of infrastructure - developing cooperation with local authorities - improving tourism - stimulating local community - peacekeeping

Geographic and historic context and cultural DNA of the sites

Two significant stećci necropolises in Montenegro, recognized as UNESCO protected cultural heritage sites, are in Žabljak. The Grcko groblje, spanning approximately 500 m², is delineated by a gentle grass meadow to the north and a local road along with Riblje jezero to the south. Adjacent to this necropolis lies a village church and a populated area, contributing to its cultural landscape. Meanwhile, Bare Zugica, situated in Novakovići, occupies slightly elevated terrain, and is flanked by the Novakovići - Njegovuđa road to the south, with a church and cemetery nearby. Despite their proximity to the town centre, these sites remain relatively underexplored in tourism and are susceptible to environmental degradation. Crafted from indigenous limestone, the stećci within these necropolises feature a rich array of decorative motifs, albeit they endure gradual weather-induced deterioration. Additionally, while hiking and biking trails are not directly accessible to these sites, there are some smaller pathways in the surrounding areas, albeit not leading directly to the stećci. In another part of Montenegro, within the Piva region, lies a third UNESCO-protected necropolis, also known as Grcko groblje. Positioned at an elevation of 908 meters in the hamlet of Zagrdje, this necropolis is nestled amidst a young beech forest on a steep slope east of Soko. Here, most of the stećci are unadorned, except for one monumental piece inscribed with the epitaph to Christian Petko. Unfortunately, despite its historical significance, this necropolis suffers from neglect and obscurity due to poor accessibility and inadequate visitor information.

Major issues

The primary challenges facing the preservation and recognition of stećci sites in Montenegro include a general lack of awareness about their cultural significance, insufficient research, and the need for cohesive strategies to engage local communities and stakeholders in their conservation. It emphasizes the importance of educating and involving the local population in tourism-related activities to ensure the sites' sustainable use and the conservation of their cultural heritage, while also addressing the difficulties of

marketing these sites in a way that attracts tourists without compromising their authenticity. Moreover, the text identifies several obstacles to achieving these goals, such as the sites' current conditions, public engagement issues, accessibility, the necessity of educating visitors about the cultural value, managing tourist numbers, bureaucratic challenges, and motivating youth participation in heritage preservation and tourism efforts for sustained interest.

Objectives

The primary objectives of the project focus on enhancing accessibility to and cataloguing of stećci to safeguard Montenegro's cultural heritage. This involves collaboration with scientific and educational institutions to raise public awareness and protect these monuments. Additionally, efforts are directed towards integrating stećci sites into sustainable cultural tourism through climate resilience planning and conservation measures. Complementary objectives include improving infrastructure for accessibility, collaborating with the local community, integrating the necropolis Greek Cemetery into tourist routes, implementing visitor tracking systems and stimulating the local economy through tourism services. Ultimately, educating the population about stećci fosters peace and social responsibility while promoting their recognition as shared cultural heritage.

Stakeholder mapping

This pilot has identified stakeholders who are representatives of public institutions such as ministries, museums, administrations dealing with the protection of cultural heritage, academia, as well as representatives of the local communities where necropolises - stećci are located. The third sector is also involved, namely non-governmental organisations dealing with cultural and creative industries, NGOs promoting the rights of vulnerable groups and NGOs dealing with inclusive tourism, as well as media representatives. As the most important stakeholders, this pilot recognizes the importance of tourist organisations and agencies, and the importance of including the Tourism Organisation of the Municipality of Žabljak and the National Tourism Organisation of Montenegro. By bringing together diverse stakeholders, including project participants, local communities, NGOs, and relevant authorities, the pilot case will facilitate dialogue, awareness-raising, and networking opportunities. UDG identified 27 stakeholders and seven users.

Vulnerable groups

Efforts for inclusion involve collaborating with NGOs focused on protecting vulnerable groups, engaging in open dialogues, and providing training to enhance their participation in tourism and heritage activities. Cultural diversity is integrated into tourism programs, while inclusion of people with disabilities requires adapting tourism programs and implementing accessible solutions for sustainable development. The pilot project aims to promote inclusive tourism by ensuring equal accessibility to tourist destinations, prioritizing individuals with disabilities, the elderly, those with chronic health conditions, parents with small children, young people, and women.

Mechanism and synergies for social inclusion

Integrating persons with disabilities into the project actively promotes inclusivity. By involving individuals with disabilities in various aspects of the project, their unique perspectives and contributions enrich the initiative while fostering a more diverse and equitable environment.

The STECCI project should strive to be inclusive and involve various groups, including older adults, individuals with chronic health conditions, parents with young children, youth, and women, and to organize events in synergy with NGOs focusing on their rights. Partnering with such NGOs allows for a targeted approach to addressing the specific needs of marginalized groups associated with the stećci heritage. These collaborations facilitate the exchange of expertise, resources, and advocacy efforts, ensuring a more comprehensive and effective approach to social inclusion within the project. These efforts aim to foster social inclusion by organizing cultural events showcasing minority traditions, celebrating diversity, and promoting equal participation.

Expected outcomes of pilot activities

The main vision entails enriching cultural heritage while advocating for the inclusion of vulnerable groups, thereby necessitating heightened visibility of stećci. It strives to establish a sustainable cultural hub centered around stećci, offering authentic experiences, promoting cultural heritage, and attaining global recognition, thus serving as a blueprint for sustainable cultural tourism.

The idea to create virtual tours of stećci necropolises aims to contribute to sustainable tourism. By leveraging virtual technology, these tours offer visitors an immersive experience, allowing them to explore the cultural and historical significance of stećci from anywhere in the world. This approach not only reduces the environmental impact associated with physical travel but also extends the accessibility of these heritage sites to a wider audience, including those who may face barriers to traditional tourism, thereby fostering a more inclusive and sustainable tourism model.

Accessibility

The Greek cemetery in Žabljak is located near a village church and populated area, surrounded by scenic elements like the lake plateau and Durmitor massif. Accessible via the regional road from Žabljak to Njegovuđa, it covers about 500 m², with stećci arranged on a slightly elevated surface. Bare Žugića, located northeast of the Grčko groblje necropolis, lies adjacent to a local road in the Novakovići hamlet, with a church and cemetery opposite it. Positioned on slightly elevated terrain, its boundaries are delineated by grassy meadows transitioning into steep slopes to the north, while roads define the southern and eastern limits, and a gentle slope with low vegetation marks the western boundary.

3.3.3 CROATIA

Pilot Case	Population	Main & complementary objectives
Cista Velika	---	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - overcome remoteness - increase visibility
Split	160,000 (2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sustainable tourism - clarifying the importance of CH - creating inclusion - awareness building

Geographic and historic context and cultural DNA of the sites

Municipality of Cista Provo, located in Split-Dalmatia County's western part known as Imotska Krajina, encompasses six settlements and occupies a plateau nearly 7 KM long at an approximate altitude of 463m. With a population of 1,799 residents identified as predominantly Croat and Catholic, covering 107.32 KM², it faces challenges such as neglected areas and misconceptions about CH, as well as insufficiently explored archaeological sites. While some sites are publicly owned, private property owners have limited opportunities to engage in heritage preservation efforts, especially considering the municipality's proximity to tourist attractions like Split and accessible pilots about 50 KM away. On the other hand, some infrastructure improvements, particularly concerning accessibility for disabled individuals, remain unaddressed by relevant authorities.

Major issues

The inadequate valorization and protection methods of the sites in the local context have resulted in significant consequences, including a lack of sustainable management perspectives for the future due to insufficient understanding of the true value, history, role, and purpose of stećci. Additionally, the erosion of the original material and information stored within the stećci individual blocks and sites presents a considerable challenge, further complicated by unclear ownership of private sites, hindering effective preservation and management efforts.

Objectives

The primary goal is to enhance pupil/student interest in stećci as well as improving access to the Necropolis by upgrading public infrastructure and increasing visibility in urban areas. Collaborating with UNSA will involve creating guidelines for monitoring and conserving limestone monuments. Complementary objectives include engaging vulnerable groups through workshops and storytelling evenings to promote inclusivity,

while efforts to mitigate site remoteness aim to raise awareness of cultural heritage significance and encourage sustainable tourism.

Stakeholder mapping

UMAS has identified a wide spectrum of stakeholders. The main stakeholders are the municipalities and their residents who represent a local community. Within that community, particularly students and pupils, or the younger population will represent the main carrier of protection of the stećci sites in the future. Among the main stakeholders are also local NGOs, schools, private landowners, the Ministry of Culture, Museum of Croatian Archaeological Monuments, the Croatian Restoration Institute, as well as the Croatian National Tourist Board. These stakeholders bring diverse but also intersecting visions.

UMAS identified 21 stakeholders and four users.

Vulnerable groups

Inclusive mechanisms have been established to engage diverse groups in cultural activities, including projects addressing sight impairments through partnerships with the Arts Academy of Split (UMAS) and storytelling programs conducted with nearby elderly homes and elderly daycare projects such as the ZAŽELI project. Additionally, creative workshops organized in collaboration with UMAS. The initiative targets various vulnerable groups, such as people with sight impairments, elderly individuals sharing their history, and individuals from nearby rehabilitation centres for addiction, with efforts to ensure accessibility and involvement through collaboration with UMAS and post-redesign initiatives for easy website access.

Expected outcome of pilot activities

The medieval sepulchral monuments known as stećci can be reinterpreted to represent cooperation and peacekeeping, offering opportunities for inclusive growth in the region due to their intercultural significance and depiction of decorative, symbolic, and religious motifs. The pilot initiative aims to integrate tangible cultural heritage into local ecosystems through community-based research strategies involving various stakeholders. These include workshops with local schools and cultural institutions, storytelling festivals and improvements to tourist infrastructure, with a focus on overcoming logistical challenges and engaging key stakeholders in sustainable cultural tourism strategies.

Accessibility

Accessibility to the stećci is given, and the site is well connected to frequent traffic routes (divided by state road d 60), but further information on barriers for people with sight impairment or wheelchair users must be collected. No proper signalization for sight impaired: they can't get to the site on their own, nor experience the site without tactile interaction with the actual monuments.

3.3.4 GERMANY

Site	Population	Main & complementary objectives
Unsleben	1,000 (2008)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - promoting the cemeteries and the history of the Jewish community - research by students on different historical topics - social inclusiveness
Kleinbardorf	300 (2008)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - conservation & restoration of stone monuments - executing social activities - accomplish sustainable tourism plans

Geographic and historic context and cultural DNA of the sites

The pilot focuses on promoting the history and heritage of two Jewish communities, Kleinbardorf and Unsleben, in northern Bavaria, Germany. Kleinbardorf, located in the Sulzfeld region since 1978, and Unsleben, part of Hay Bedding, both belong to the Grabfeld district of Rhön. Despite being about 15.5 KM apart, they are accessible by bus or car in approximately 25 minutes. Kleinbardorf boasts archaeological heritage dating back to 10,000 BC, including an ancient settlement and an old connecting road from the 8th century. Its medieval Jewish cemetery, the Judenhügel, served 27 communities until the 20th century and is one of Bavaria's largest. Conversely, Unsleben's main synagogue, first mentioned in 1162, was destroyed in 1938, but the town's Jewish cemetery, documented by several institutions, reflects its rich historical heritage. The pilot aims to preserve and promote these landmarks through local social initiatives, cultural events, workshops, and conservation measures, integrating them into the communities of Kleinbardorf and Unsleben.

Major issues

Both cemeteries, owned by the Jewish Religious Community, necessitate permission for access despite their apparent neglect. While the Kleinbardorf cemetery is overgrown and difficult to reach, especially for disabled and elderly individuals, the Unsleben cemetery benefits from a digitization project, providing a virtual tour and improved accessibility. Both sites are registered with the Bavarian State Office of Monument Preservation.

Objectives

The main objectives of the pilot in Germany involve surveying, preserving, and managing the medieval Jewish cemeteries in Kleinbardorf and Unsleben. Additionally, the project aims to engage schools in non-invasive documentation of gravestones, promote sustainable socio-tourist communities, and scientifically manage the cultural heritage of the gravestones using multidisciplinary techniques and high technology for

documentation and public accessibility. The pilot in Kleinbardorf and Unsleben includes complementary objectives such as conducting research by students on historical topics, organizing roundtables and storytelling sessions for social and cultural integration, holding practical workshops on conservation, documenting the cemeteries using advanced methods, involving school students in basic documentation techniques, and developing a sustainable tourism plan.

Stakeholder mapping

Stakeholders were identified at this site from federal ministries for monument protection, heritage conservationists, the municipality itself and schools. The most important of these is the Jewish community whose participation would ensure the decisive success in this case. Stakeholders from Israel were also recruited. To engage the Jewish community, SPK plans to initiate a dialogue with the Johanna Stahl Zentrum which actively seeks cooperation in the field of cultural memory and has a special focus on cemeteries in Lower Franconia.

SPK has identified twelve stakeholders and three users.

Vulnerable groups

To overcome the challenges faced by people with disabilities, virtual tours are conducted, and accessibility is improved through collaboration with local tourism providers. Promoting inclusion within the Jewish community includes collaboration and workshops offered by the Jewish Cultural Centre and the Johanna Stahl Centre.

Mechanism and synergies for social inclusion

The plan prioritizes enhancing accessibility for a diverse range of groups, including visitors without car access, utilizing brainstorming sessions and workshops to generate ideas for pedestrian and cyclist accessibility improvements, while also collaborating with the Jewish Cultural Centre to address vulnerabilities within the Jewish community, aligning with broader objectives to foster social responsibility and promoting inclusion and dialogue within the population.

Expected outcome of pilot activities

The pilot's focus is on fostering unity and continuity between the past and present through the preservation of the sites in Kleinbardorf and Unsleben, aiming to involve various community sectors, such as students, parents, and government bodies, in the sustainable development of historical resources. Furthermore, it seeks to raise awareness and encourage community engagement in the preservation of Jewish cemeteries, utilizing them as educational tools to highlight their historical significance and promote sustainable tourism. This comprehensive approach benefits schools, congregations, and the Jewish community, emphasizing the importance of preserving cemetery history and enhancing accessibility through initiatives like virtual tours.

Accessibility

The Jewish cemetery in Kleinbardorf is accessible primarily by car, with a driving time of approximately 3 minutes from the village center to a specific point near the cemetery. However, reaching the cemetery itself requires walking, and there are no resting points such as benches along the route. The presence of vegetation and trees may impede movement, particularly for elderly individuals. In contrast, access to the Unsleben Jewish cemetery is relatively easier. It takes about 4 minutes by car from the center of Unsleben, with no public transportation available. From the main road, it's a 5-minute walk to reach the cemetery. However, both sites lack accessibility for elderly and disabled individuals. To address this issue, well-paved routes with infrastructure catering to disabled persons should be provided, along with the consideration of implementing public transportation options for easier access.

3.3.5 SERBIA

Site	Description	Main & complementary objectives
Serbia	4,100 stones in 203 locations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - education programs - analysing the impacts CC - protection of CH - increasing tourism potential

Geographic and historic context and cultural DNA of the sites

There are 2,634 immovable cultural assets registered in Serbia, including cultural monuments, spatial cultural-historical units, archaeological sites, and famous places. Among them, the Stećci, medieval tombstones found in 203 locations, are of exceptional importance. Serbia is strongly committed to the preservation of this heritage, involving various institutions such as the Ministry of Culture and local cultural institutions. This commitment is reflected in regular inspections and conservation measures, including chemical treatments that are supervised by experts. In addition, there is a remarkable public interest in stećci, which is evident through regular tourist offers from various agencies.

Major issues

After stećci was declared a cultural asset of outstanding importance in Serbia, efforts have been made to develop teaching materials that integrate science to address the conservation of stećak. The initial focus is on presenting experiments and discussing the connection between environmental concerns and the preservation of cultural heritage to subsequently raise the cultural and environmental awareness of those involved, especially schoolchildren.

Objectives

The major objectives of the project are to develop integrative educational materials focusing on natural sciences, using stećak conservation as a case study, and to test these materials in workshops involving teachers and students. These workshops aim to address challenges in preserving cultural heritage amidst climate change, incorporate interdisciplinary knowledge, and raise awareness about the importance of conserving stećak and other cultural assets. Complementary objectives involve presenting the educational materials in public exhibitions to promote awareness and individual responsibility for heritage preservation, while also leveraging these sites to enhance tourism potential and foster economic growth. Additionally, through social engagement and themed events, the project aims to achieve specific goals such as promoting intergenerational cohesion.

Stakeholder

The stakeholders involved in this project cover a broad spectrum of sectors: there are representatives of tourism boards, higher education, media, public authorities, as well as cultural and creative industries.

UNSPMF has currently identified 19 stakeholders and seven users.

Vulnerable groups

In this demo site vulnerable groups will be primarily children and young people.

Mechanism and synergies for social inclusion

The educational material developed can be used by various stakeholders, including schools and museums to tailor workshops to the needs of participants, promote universality across different countries and engage specific groups of students, prioritise the promotion of inter- and multiculturalism by targeting vulnerable or marginalized populations.

Expected outcome of pilot activities

The main objective is to develop educational materials for students and other interested individuals, emphasize intergenerational cohesion in educational workshops, and promote collaboration with churches to support peacekeeping initiatives. The aim is to produce a variety of materials to raise awareness among schools and various stakeholders about the importance of heritage conservation and the factors that influence it.

Accessibility

The stećci in Serbia are under the protection of the state, and since they are recognized as an important tourist potential, easy access, i.e. access to the road, is already given. In this pilot case, further research activities will focus on the accessibility as part of the activities in T5.2.

4. STECCI LAB APPROACH

After researching the literature and identifying the stakeholders, the individual pilots were discussed with the partners in collaborative brainstorming meetings to obtain more detailed information about regional and national circumstances and to create tailor-made capacity building. The task involves developing a robust methodology and a transdisciplinary laboratory manual that caters to both experts and non-professional volunteers alike. The laboratory serves as a venue for collaborative research and social experiments involving multiple stakeholders, aiming to address complex social challenges at a systemic level. The STECCI Lab approach involves the equal participation of local and regional stakeholders, as well as research and innovation partners of the consortium, and includes a mapping analysis to identify local needs, challenges, potentials, and best practices.

4.1 STECCI LABS – UNDERLYING CONCEPTS

In STECCI the social labs approach is further developed. In general, social labs connect diverse practices and people who are affected by shared problems in various ways. The methodology provides space for doing transdisciplinary interventions and social experiments in a practical context where researchers, professional experts and civil society representatives initiate actions in a structured but dynamic process (Hassan 2014). Labs bring in a real-world focus (i.e. Timmermans et al. 2020) and offer an agile approach based on practice-led research and experiential learning. There is a subsequent learning process through experiences and ‘learning through reflection on doing’ (i.e. Felicia 2011); furthermore, it brings together stakeholders from science and practice to develop and try out scientifically and socially robust solutions based on a common understanding of the problem.

The STECCI social innovation lab concept follows a people-centric and participatory approach in an experimental environment, bringing together actors from science and practice to develop and try out solutions based on a common understanding of needs and constraints. The main objective is to foster solutions and co-create socially innovative solutions to community or region related needs.

As described in chapter 3, STECCI stakeholders are defined as actors coming from quadruple helix (QH) collaboration. In the specific case of pilots, labs provide new forms of cooperation with a focus on science and civil society. All applied participatory methodologies are flexible in terms of research procedures and implementation that depend on the specifics of local settings of the pilot cases. One strategy is to involve stakeholders from the start to identify problems and incorporate relevant needs, interests, and different forms of knowledge such as academic, professional, traditional, every day and tacit knowledge or embodied knowledge or emotional attachments to the places without hierarchizing them. To foster and benefit from these diverse forms of knowledge, the labs will host a series of activities with structured and open-ended components. Especially, forms of creative and design thinking are applied to

contribute to different outcomes such as the STECCI virtual tours (T4.4), the STECCI serious game (T4.2) and the STECCI policy briefs on cultural heritage and cultural tourism.

Every lab includes a bundle of interlinked main activities which will be aligned with site-specific needs, while the context analysis (with the help of a World Café with multi-stakeholders) and a storytelling session are obligatory for each STECCI lab.

Fig. 13: STECCI social innovation labs

Multi-stakeholder involvement is fundamental to address social challenges and requires a proactive approach within the STECCI framework to establish, promote and sustain social labs involving municipalities, schools, and communities.

Social (innovation) labs typically involve a variety of participants from QH with different backgrounds and interests. Lab hosts lead the lab sessions and workshops, support collaboration and effective communication, and lead collaborative efforts to generate ideas and concrete actions to address previously identified challenges.

4.2 METHODS FOR CO-CREATION & CITIZEN SCIENCE

Co-creation follows a community-based strategy. This strategy addresses the site-specific and social dimensions of stećci tombstones. To enable participation of volunteers from civil society, co-creation and citizen science were identified as appropriate approaches, taking advantage of the expertise of volunteers, and taking care of their needs equally. All activities follow a participatory and transdisciplinary approach which mirrors the need to align with the social layer of the cultural heritage artefacts through a place-based approach connecting volunteer researchers more closely with stećci and direct environments. Moreover, it creates new understandings of what these places mean, and encourage stakeholders to participate more fully as stewards and caretakers of those places (i.e. Toomey et al. 2020)

Co-creation actively involves relevant stakeholders in the entire process. The key concept is that users such as citizens or community members are experts in their own experiences and day-to-day life. In co-creation, community members actively shape solutions, going beyond the usual involvement as mere data sources or consultation partners. Co-creation is based on the concept that research and design is not done at the command of users but in collaboration. Furthermore, co-creation includes open-ended and creative components to enable innovation including social innovation. The third phase of co-production focuses on a joint planning – stakeholders are involved as a reflexive working group – and the implementation to generate best results together with the project consortium.

STECCI LAB*CO-CREATION PROCESS

Fig. 14: Co-creation process and methodologies

Citizen science is defined as a structured research process, in which citizens, who are not institutionally anchored in science, participate in knowledge production beyond their role as respondents or research subjects. This approach combines the intelligence and creativity of volunteer researchers. Citizens can contribute to all research phases, including the definition of the problem or the scope, the research question, the research design, the research implementation, the data collection, the analysis, the interpretation, and the presentation of results.

CO-CREATION & PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES (Citizen social sciences, AR, science shops)

Fig. 15: Citizen science approach (Pamela Bartar 2022)

In STECCI citizen science activities are implemented together with volunteer researchers i.e. aged 11-16 years in a school context doing joint and disciplinary diverse experiments as well as science communication activities such as reverse science cafés and pop-up science shops in STECCI related topics. Moreover, participatory research methods implemented in STECCI can include shared mapping walks, design thinking for ideation like worst possible idea exercise, storytelling like the appreciative inquiry format, future visioning and social dreaming, the pro action café format and scenario building, as well as the world café format, which is used in the kick-off phase of the STECCI labs.

In the following, methods are explained in an alphabetical order. As the kick-off phase of STECCI SI labs might bring up additional research topics, as well as feedback by participants, further methods can be identified during the lab activities. The following figure gives an overview on the appropriate identified methods.

PHASES OF SOCIAL INNOVATION:

EXPLORATION, EMPATHIZE, DISCUSS (1) | IDEATION (2) | DESIGN, PLAN, PROTOTYPE (3) | TEST, IMPLEMENT (4) | DISSEMINATION (5)

Fig. 16: Methods in the research phases of the STECCI labs

4.2.1 ACTIVATING SURVEY (INTERVIEWS)

In the context of STECCI, an activating survey asks stakeholders about their opinions, key interests, networks and at the same time encourages them to participate in the development of solutions of their living environment and the labs. The survey is kept uncomplicated and open. At the same time, this method makes it possible to convey information about planned projects and to react to possible critical positions. Every pilot lab or demo site leader is asked to interview at least four stakeholders representing the most important stakeholder groups linked to quadruple helix.

The method aims at getting people to address issues that are relevant to them. The outreach form of the method is primarily intended to reach people who do not usually or rarely get involved. The bottom-up orientation is a key principle of the method. People should not be recruited for a specific participation project, but rather they are asked what concerns/issues they themselves are concerned with. The approach is usually used in defined areas such as in an organisation, district, or neighbourhood. The goal is to support people in articulating the issues and in collectivizing and organizing their interests. Activating surveys in each pilot hosting a lab are also expected to enhance the preliminary stakeholder mapping. Furthermore, key developments in the regions can be analysed in a timely manner.

Phase/s: explore, empathize, discuss (1)

Target group/s: all stakeholder groups in QH; practitioners including artists, designers, planners, architects, cultural workers, social entrepreneurs, citizens of all age groups and backgrounds, policymakers, representatives from NGO and CSO researchers

Space: onsite or online

Duration: 30 min-1.5 h

Relevance to stećci pilots: The activating survey can promote the project in the beginning of the co-creation process and helps to learn more about the stećci heritage seen from the community perspective. The method enables to collect further information about challenges and needs or expectations from all stakeholder groups to prepare a lab agenda. It can be used for snowballing and helps to identify further stakeholders of relevance.

4.2.2 APPRECIATIVE INQUIRY

Instead of taking a problem-solving approach, appreciative inquiry offers a possibility focus, a move from “what is” to “what could be”. It is a flexible format in which groups are guided to plan and implement changes together. The special feature here is the focus on appreciating the achievements and strengths of a project, a group, or an organisation, instead of the usual deficits and weaknesses. As a first step, the moderator asks questions and leads a discussion. The participants answer the questions either in groups of three or four or individually. They write their answers on index cards and then present the results to the group. Once the questions from the first step have been worked through and a positive mood has been achieved, the group can move on to the second step of problem solving.

Phase/s: explore, empathize, discuss (1)

Target group/s: practitioners including artists, designers, planners, architects, cultural workers, social entrepreneurs, citizens of all age groups and backgrounds, policy makers, representatives from NGO and CSO researchers

Space: onsite or online

Duration: 1.5 h to half day

Relevance to stećci pilots: This method helps to gain quickly new insights and empowers a mixed group of experts and community members in the pilots working together. Stećci heritage is linked to tangible or intangible and local aspects, which can contribute to a new region-based historiography and experiential learning in the social labs.

4.2.3 CREATIVE PLACEMAKING

This approach can be described as a new way of engaging creative people and activities to address social and economic issues in communities. Projects can focus on connecting local history with the present, bringing cultural influences into the spotlight, and creating new traditions. Creative placemaking will activate public spaces or create a short-term opportunity to connect residents around arts and culture. It is also a new way of engaging creative people and activities to address social and economic issues in communities. Additionally, creative placemaking can use the arts and cultural activities to rejuvenate public places.

Examples can be the participatory curation of an exhibition, guided tours on green topic or art history, an open mic performance to activate the speak-out of a community in the public space, an art-craft market by local artists and designers or a historic re-enactment. Creative placemaking is closely linked to the dissemination and exploitation of a site-specific or place-based topic and can activate the public discourse.

Phase/s: all (1-5)

Target group/s: practitioners including artists, designers, planners, architects, cultural workers, citizens of all age groups and backgrounds, researchers

Space: onsite

Duration: 2 h to several days

Relevance to stećci pilots: This method is helpful in pilots with little development sites around stećci and brings the local needs into the centre of endeavors. Creativity-led activities facilitate new approaches to the CH and the sites and link – also literally spoken – the stećci with the environment and the neighborhoods.

4.2.4 DOCUMENT STUDY

This method involves a detailed review of the documents to extract themes or patterns relevant to the research topic. It is a systematic procedure for reviewing or evaluating scientific articles and beyond. In the latter case, documents can be defined as social facts that are produced, shared, and used in socially organised ways. They can include advertisements, agendas, attendance registers, manuals; background papers, books and brochures, diaries and journals, event programs, letters and memoranda, maps and charts, newspapers, press releases, program proposals, application forms and summaries, radio and television program scripts, organisational or institutional reports, survey data and various public records. Scrapbooks and photo albums can also furnish documentary material for research purposes. These types of documents are found in libraries, newspaper archives, historical society offices, and organisational or institutional files. The analysis of documents helps STECCI researchers, lab participants and citizen scientists to understand and categorize primary sources. Researchers use this approach to equally gather ideas and evidence.

Phase/s: explore, empathize, discuss (1)

Target group/s: researchers, practitioners including artists, designers, cultural workers or citizens of all age groups and backgrounds

Space: onsite

Duration: 2 h to half day

Relevance to stećci pilots: This method contributes to the collaborative research on stećci in the scientific and the day-to-day context. It was applied in T5.1 as a general literature analysis and can be further enhanced through the collection of materials such as touristic information folders or maps contributing with another layer of data. In the context of co-creation and creativity-workshops, examples are a collage or a

morphological box for arts-informed research and presentation. The results can be used as content for a science shop or a roaming exhibition to promote stećci in all pilot regions and beyond.

4.2.5 PARTICIPATORY DESIGN THINKING

This is a democratic approach that can involve STECCI SI lab participants as users in the design process (social, technological, ecological etc.) of artefacts, concepts, services, or seed projects in the labs initiated by participants themselves, ensuring more relevant, accessible, and inclusive outcomes. This does not only require the participation in decision making but also in the idea generation. Participatory design principles emphasize the importance of co-creation and collaboration between artists, cultural institutions, and communities. Participants are invited to cooperate during the complete innovation process through workshops, consultations, and community-led initiatives. Another aspect is to empower marginalised communities that have traditionally been excluded from the decision-making processes to play an active role.

In STECCI SI labs participatory design thinking can be applied in the complete design process to enable social innovation. Methods supporting the ideation are foreseen in the initial phase of the STECCI SI labs. For example, the Worst Possible Idea exercise is a brainstorming method to quickly generate ideas or research questions through coming up with as many bad ideas as possible that can be used for all participants of all ages and backgrounds. Another method in this framework is the Persona-Based Walkthrough helping participants to change their perspective and foster potential advantages and disadvantages for other stakeholder groups than one's own, helping to align products, concepts, and services etc.

Phase/s: all (except dissemination 5)

Target group/s: mixed expert group including researchers, practitioners, including artists, designers, architects, planners, teachers, cultural managers, tourism managers

Space: onsite

Duration: 2 h to half day

Relevance to stećci pilots: This method provides different approaches for the entire innovation process in STECCI and enables community-based interventions and socially innovative solutions due to its participatory character. The approach can be used as a design thinking cycle or highlight specific phases. In the STECCI labs, participants can decide, which of the interventions are of relevance to their local stećci site and enable the valorisation of the CH due to their expectations and ideas.

4.2.6 PARTICIPATORY OBSERVATION

Participatory or community-based observing methodologies produce environmental data in a social context and are also well suited to provide empirical data. Community-based observing groups are methodologies developed from collaborations between community members, researchers, and government agencies. The term “community-based observing” describes methodologies used to report on social and environmental variables by teams of researchers and place-based observers. The data collection and reporting protocols are co-created by communities and researchers, producing linked social and environmental data in interoperable formats that can embed biophysical data in social contexts. Methodologies have the potential to produce empirical data for social–ecological systems research in many regions of the world.

Phase/s: explore, empathize, discuss (1) test, implement (4)

Target group/s: citizens, researchers

Space: onsite

Duration: half day to several days

Relevance to stećci pilots: This method contributes to the data collection including i.e. the number of visitors during a certain period or of animals living in the natural stećci ecosystem or collect probes from vegetation; it is helpful to monitor the necropolis in the context of natural hazards or vandalism during all seasons. It could be also used in the pilots on citizen science collaboratively doing research with schools during one semester. Community-based observation has the potential to raise the awareness of the communities and further stakeholder groups.

4.2.7 POP-UP SCIENCE SHOPS

This event format engages citizens, civil society organisations and research institutions. The Pop-up Science Shop refers to a single event simulating the way how civil society makes requests and how these problems can be transferred into a research setup. Citizens are called clients in the context of the “shop”. Science Shops enable that research is done based on concerns of civil society and that projects are governed in a partnership between civil society organisations (CSOs) and research institutes. Science Shops mediate mutual learning and cooperation processes. By engaging different groups and organisations idea of responsiveness and diversity. The research question development is based on anticipation, reflection, adaptation, and reflectivity.

Phase/s: explore, empathize, discuss (1)

Target group/s: non-expert citizens with a focus on children, students, families, seniors

Space: onsite

Duration: half day to several days

Relevance to stećci pilots: Pop-up Science Shops make research results and creative outcomes visible to a public audience and activate stakeholders in nearby villages and cities. The shops can be a meeting point for excursions or a meeting space for events.

4.2.8 PRO ACTION CAFÉ

The method is characterized by the free choice of topics: Whatever is relevant to the participants is discussed. The method adopts the setting of small roundtables, in which different four people sit and work together in three rounds, each 20 to 30 minutes. Collegial consultation and case work are also incorporated: some participants work on specific concerns or projects; the remaining participants take on the role of advisors and moderator who remains at the table after the round ends to inspire the next group. Together, participants explore what the discussed topic or concern is about, what gaps or challenges exist and what next steps can be taken to implement it.

Phase/s: explore, empathize, discuss (1) ideation (2) design, plan, prototype (3)

Target group/s: mixed expert groups such as policy makers, representatives from civil society organisations, researchers, practitioners such as designers, artists, architects, planners, teachers, cultural managers, tourism representatives, community members

Space: onsite

Duration: half day

Relevance to stećci pilots: This is another method to bring together STECCI multi-stakeholders to brainstorm on stećci and plan together interventions in the labs. The method goes beyond consultation and enables participants to become active for a sensitive valorisation plan. In case local decision takers from policy sphere and administration participate in the Pro Action Café, the setting can empower the community to define objectives and implementation plans, how to use this cultural heritage for social innovation and cultural tourism.

4.2.9 REVERSE SCIENCE CAFÉ

This approach is a discussion event focused on various ethical and societal topics related to local examples of research, technology, and innovation in the context of stećci and the project. The dialogue is initiated by experts posing questions and listening to answers from the audience. Together they work in small groups to formulate their advice on making research and innovation more responsible. The method helps to engage non-experts with new scientific topics and findings and to revise ongoing research in a responsive manner.

Phase/s: explores, empathize, discuss (1) ideation (2) dissemination (5)

Target group/s: non-expert citizens with a focus on children, students, families, seniors, and researchers

Space: onsite

Duration: 1 h to half day (depends on the number of participants)

Relevance to stećci pilots: The Reverse Science Café can be used to test and present project findings for the STECCI capacity building programs or a festival. It offers a way to share different perspectives and to learn from the local community and external CH experts or CH practitioners, equally. The Café is a creative learning and teaching method applied in the context of the labs and the summer schools. Furthermore, it is an innovative approach to gain valuable feedback on the agenda and the content of summer schools to further align with the needs of participants.

4.2.10 SCENARIO BUILDING

A scenario workshop is a participatory method encouraging local action with a mix of scenario and workshop which aims to solve local problems and anticipate future ones. Scenarios involve narrative descriptions of potential future problems that emphasize relationships between events and decision points. The scenario workshop is a method in which participants from a local community engage in discussion, produce some sort of action through deliberative discussion and act as decision-makers or create a communal plan of action.

The goal of a scenario workshop is to create dialogue among policymakers, experts, and ordinary citizens around a local and communal matter. Scenarios as a decision-making tool help us to better understand the implications of a wide range of future possibilities considering existing development and upcoming strategies. Scenarios should be co-produced with users including practitioners such as planners or civil society representatives. In a scenario building process, users together with researchers create alternative versions of future governance set-ups and respective socio-economic development with respect to a jointly framed problem.

Phase/s: design, plan, prototype (3)

Target group/s: mixed expert groups such as policy makers, policy influencers from civil society organisations, practitioners such as designers, artists, architects, planners, teachers, cultural managers, tourism representatives

Space: onsite or online

Duration: half day to full day

Relevance to stećci pilots: The method helps to validate new ideas and concepts in the pilots for the valorisation of stećci. After the community-led research and a speculative idea generation on what can be done, the scenario building workshop with policy makers and further decision takers is expected to guide how to reach objectives or redefine objectives to the local or regional agenda. It can be used for short-, mid- or long-term concepts.

4.2.11 SCI-ART EXPERIMENTS

This method is about using art to explore science and to engage with art. Sci-Art can be an interdisciplinary workshop about science, space and society, where art is used to explore scientific concepts and humanity's relationship to it. Participants learn how scientists use different methods like observations, how to access data and how to do inter- and transdisciplinary collaborative discussion and art activities. They learn approaches to create science-driven art through hands-on artmaking "labs." This approach is about learning by creating, and the role artists can play in science, research, and innovation exploration. Art-making activities utilize a range of mediums, and most are flexible allowing participants to explore using either new or familiar methods.

Phase/s: explore, empathize, discuss (1) design, plan prototype (3) test, implement (4)

Target group/s: non-expert citizens with a focus on children, students, families, seniors

Space: onsite

Duration: 1 h to half day (dependent on the number of experiments during one workshop)

Relevance to stećci pilots: The approach is useful to involve schools and families into science communication activities with experiments in conservation and chemistry or biology to foster the natural environments of the stećci sites. It can encompass complex experiments or simple installations with video or photo collages, or a morphologic box of knowledge related to stećci. It can be created together with local or regional artists and researchers from the consortium. Moreover, it can engage the community with its research and creativity through collaborative methods such as the participatory observation and the mapping walk.

4.2.12 SOCIAL / DRAGON DREAMING

Both approaches have the goal to transform dream of thinking by means of free association, thematic amplification, and systemic thinking to find links, make connections, and generate new thoughts. Social dreaming is mainly anchored into the brainstorming phase and takes place in a so-called matrix, a container that captures the echoes of thoughts situated in the space of the many-in-the-mind, where participants connect with the social, cultural, and natural environment.

Dragon Dreaming contains a pool of methods to generate "dreams" for sustainable projects and follow four phases including the dreaming, the planning, the implementation, and the celebration of results. Social and Dragon Dreaming make use of emotional knowledge.

Phase/s: ideation (2) design, plan, prototype (3) test, implement (4)

Target group/s: mixed non-expert groups including influencers from civil society organisations, and practitioners such as designers, artists, architects, planners, teachers, cultural managers, tourism representatives

Space: onsite or online

Duration: 2 h to half day; in the concept of Dragon Dreaming the implementation can be sequential over a longer period than one day.

Relevance to stećci pilots: Social dreaming enables the imagination of the local stakeholders using stećci as a vessel of inspiration or as a starting point for a 'social dream'. While scenario building workshops focus on the feasibility of ideas on the ground, social dreaming opens the floor for positive utopia. This can be related to social innovation and social entrepreneurship in cultural tourism in the more remote stećci sites. There are no limits to the fantasy, when it comes to improve the social context and to involve vulnerable groups. Social dreaming can be implemented in a more complex manner with experts and practitioners in CH related fields or as happening with families. Moreover, local, or regional artists can take over a facilitating role transferring ideas into artefacts or concepts into appealing stories for exhibitions. The community members can vote for the best ideas to be implemented in the village or to be presented during an exhibition or festival to gain visibility.

4.2.13 STORYTELLING

This method is a systematic process in which content is emotionalized using dramaturgical structures and implicit information stored in the recipient's memory for the long term. Storytelling is also a method to make site-specific, traditional, tacit, and embodied knowledge visible and enabling mutual learning. A story can communicate certain innovations, values, cultural aspects, best practices, and lessons learned. Storytelling includes variations based on structure, texture, language, and media; it can be fostered and presented digitally in the form of podcasts or video reels and distributed via social media

Phase/s: explore, empathize, discuss (1) test, implement (4) dissemination (5)

Target group/s: non-expert citizens including children, seniors and other vulnerable or marginalized groups and influential community members

Space: onsite, online

Duration: 1 h to half day (depends on the number of sessions during the workshop)

Relevance to stećci pilots: This method helps to gain insights from local communities and can be implemented in form of oral history or visual narratives on stećci. By raising awareness for the historic and transregional character, storytelling can be used as a creative technique for peace communication. Furthermore, the STECCI storytelling workshops contribute to the script drafting of the virtual tours and the serious game.

4.2.14 WORLD CAFÉ

This method is a way to find out what major stakeholder groups or a community are thinking about a topic or the objectives and expected solutions on a project like STECCI. It is helpful to bring different disciplines,

scientists and practitioners, professionals, and practitioners together. The format imitates a café setting where small groups (four or five people) are all conversing together around tables. A cluster of small groups are in conversation about a chosen issue that matters to them, for example site-specific needs, local interests, regional challenges. After the first conversation, someone stays at the table as 'host', while the others move to a new table, taking their previous conversations with them. In this way, the threads of the various conversations are brought together, and a big picture of the discussions can arise.

Phase/s: explore, empathize, discuss (1)

Target group/s: experts and non-experts from quadruple helix

Space: onsite, with some limitations also online

Duration: 1.5 h to half day (depends on the number of participants and questions)

Relevance to stećci pilots: During the STECCI lab kick-off events, the method enables an appropriate context analysis, needs assessment and supports the lab building. Participants shall be informed about possibilities to contribute to and to benefit from STECCI. It can bring together innovative partnerships between different fields, sectors, and disciplines as well as academic experts, practitioners, and citizens.

4.3 STECCI LAB: SET-UP, DESIGN, ACTIVITIES AND ROLES

The STECCI SI lab process spans a period of about one year during T5.2 (M8–21). During this period, three workshops or activities are organised in each lab, and include the phases (1) initiation & preliminary research, (2) preparation, (3) workshops and (4) documentation & exploitation after the workshops. The first phase involves investing resources to support the co-creation and implementation of pilots capable of generating impact – all efforts were started in T5.1 with the help of all consortium partners involved in WP5 co-designing the approach and methods. The recruitment process and the field research are the main steps (as well as phase 4) in the second phase and starts in T5.2. Social innovation labs bring together persons from HQ with specific expertise, needs, concerns, and expectations. Participants are empowered to act on their own expectations and towards creative ideas. In the third phase, there is a series of workshops with co-creation, collaborative knowledge production and further engaging activities. They are designed to engage participants, explore the context, and facilitate new perspectives on the problems. The final goal of the workshops and engagement activities is to select one or more ideas for real-world use and pilot testing. Transferred to the STECCI labs this encompasses six main objectives linked to activities:

- Context and user studies and determining social, ecological, legal or technical and economic constraints, updating the STECCI stakeholder engagement strategy,
- Raising awareness and building knowledge on STECCI through citizen science or participatory community-based research and transferring knowledge through science communication,
- Using techniques such as creative placemaking and creative storytelling to contribute to STECCI virtual tours (T4.4) and the STECCI educational (serious) game (T4.2),

- Co-designing cultural management innovations involving CH practitioners and researchers,
- Testing research and learning scenarios for the STECCI CH management capacity building,
- Building a local and transregional STECCI community of interest.

Complementary objectives and activities will be co-designed with lab participants addressing site- and community-specific needs and interests.

To enable lab participants to be creative on finding solutions to real-world problems, STECCI labs follow a structured concept with clear roles and responsibilities. The lab managing teams include a manager, a facilitator, and a community representative. Lab managers are the main contact persons responsible for recruiting and communicating with participants, taking care of coordination, supporting lab activities and logistics. Facilitators are the responsible moderators during the lab workshops who choose methods and event formats to facilitate the dialogue between lab participants. Here, the community representative is an important contact person supporting both the manager and the facilitator with key local knowledge.

4.3.1 TOOLKIT

This is a toolkit with instructions for using and applying diverse support materials in the STECCI labs. The collection is hands-on and enables stakeholder and community engagement activities and practical set-up of events and activities. It can be used to plan, kick-off and facilitate the workshop series in all five pilot cases. The toolkit is available online on the EMDESK cloud and includes:

- STECCI labs kick-off plan
- Invitation letter
- General STECCI presentation pptx.
- Agenda template
- Participant list template
- Event documentation template
- World Café table documentation template
- Additional workshop templates
- Ice-breaker exercise (presentation or template)
- Code of conduct
- Informed consent
- Poster (or other promotional materials)

Fig. 17: Path to toolkit and SL folders on EMDESK

The toolkit is made available in the beginning of T5.2 and will be updated according to the on-the-ground needs of the STECCI labs. To further facilitate the set-up of labs and research activities, EMDESK offers dedicated pilot folders to collect documentation and data collected during the event series. All materials are provided in English and shall be customized and translated to local languages by pilot leaders if needed.

4.3.2 SUCCESS FACTORS FOR STECCI

To ensure the success, a risk and mitigation plan will be worked out by pilot lead partners at the beginning of T5.2. The plan is a tool to align with dynamic developments in the pilots to reach key performance indicators (KPIs).

In any case, the most important success factor is a clear mandate given to participants ensuring effectiveness and influence in the entire process following the inherent people- and community-centered approach of STECCI. In all innovation and co-creation processes of WP5 the goal is to gain multi-perspective input and needs-based feedback to methods, concepts, or new services. This aims to improve living circumstances such as the well-being of the community or regeneration of the locality and the region. The consortium, which is to be understood as a transdisciplinary expert team, must be open to deal with participant input and consider them in the decision-making process of the STECCI project.

One important goal of the STECCI lab is to build a local and transregional community of interest supporting a long-term commitment by lab participants to take-up results after the project end. This means that key stakeholders from community or region are kept involved throughout the entire innovation process. It is important that all participants are informed about new developments and the outcome of the process.

Therefore, lab hosts need to ask during the kick-off workshops and the World Café table sessions, **which sort of follow-up exchange can be beneficial and useful for stakeholders?**

4.3.3 TRANSFER OF KNOWLEDGE AND DOWNSTAGING OF EXPERT INFORMATION

For the kick-off event with the World Café, which is a mandatory element of the STECCI lab event series, it is recommended to use an icebreaker for activation and to start rapidly with the multistakeholder team building. Pilot partners are advised to keep the project introduction short, exemplary, and interactive. Non-academic stakeholders like to gain an overview on innovative solutions, practices, and potential benefits. STECCI labs and citizen science pilots are defined as venues for mutual learning and transdisciplinary knowledge transfer. In this context, knowledge transfer refers to transferring of evidence and practical skills between different entities – in case of STECCI, lab participants. The profile of transfer depends on the type of knowledge to be transferred and how it is represented, and the processing demands of the transfer task (see also D5.1 chapter on methods).

In particular, interactive elements and visualisation – such as providing maps, knowledge graphs or photos covering stecci – support the imagination and creativity of participants to engage themselves in innovation

processes. Maps, post-its and further materials can be used to cluster participant input and generate systematic access to place-based knowledge.

This can be transferred to place-based learning activities that include the types of experientials, community-based and environmental education. This sort of place-based education differs from conventional text education in that it understands the local community as one of the primary resources for learning. In this context, STECCI lab participants can be also understood as a living archive – lab hosts become a librarian working not only for the STECCI project but for the community.

4.3.4 WORKSHOP DOCUMENTATION AND PROTOCOLS FOR PARTICIPANTS

Stakeholders from all QH groups should be invited to the lab kick-off event. In case the participant group is big enough (at least 12 participants), a delegation leader per World Café discussion group (also in similar formats) can summarize to the plenary. During the process, visualization can help to keep everybody “on track”. That can be done by writing important aspects down on a flipchart, table paper and cards, or writing a summary of the protocol via screen. Table protocols should be collected after the workshop and stored at the EMDESK cloud. These documents are the basis for the overall documentation of the lab and citizen science workshops in D5.2 (M21) – same time the main source for the results protocol is made available to the participants.

In the discussions and further lab activities, the names of the participants are not given in the protocol. After the event, the results protocol shall be given to the participants within 20 days. It is also important that other parties can inform themselves about the interim results, i.e. stakeholders from policymaking, who learned from word of mouth or press releases.

4.3.5 STECCI LAB ETHICS: SELF-ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS

Research ethics can be defined as the principles and rules that guide how people should be treated when they are participants in a research process or project. In a social innovation lab, it might be difficult to anticipate all of the research ethics issues that may arise, but it is important to be sensitive to the people involved. Some aspects shall be considered from the beginning:

- Are the findings presented in an accessible and meaningful way to the community members?
- How is it ensured that the participants in the on-site community are not harmed during the research and gain as much benefit as possible through their participation?
- Who represents the community? Is there one voice of the community?
- Do the participants represent only some of the social identities in the community overall? Are there institutional, organisational, or other social dynamics that privilege some voices over others? Will some portions of the community benefit more than others as a result?

- How are the results represented? Whose voice(s) are heard and represented? Who receives credit for the work conducted?
- How will you responsibly make the data available to the different community and other stakeholders?
- How does 'equity' in the process translate into divisions of labour on the project/process? Is the work divided equitably among partners?
- Do all members of the community have equal opportunity to participate in the research? Are there some participants who are unfairly impacted by the research?
- How can you protect privacy in the data collection and sharing process? Did you get adequate permission from participants? Do they understand and agree with the way you plan to use the data?
- Does the presentation (or presenter) of findings in any way reinforce negative social stereotypes in the presenting communities?
- Are the findings being presented accurately? Are they presented with any bias or in a way to make people hear what they want to hear?

4.3.6 CODE OF CONDUCT FOR STECCI LABS

To establish a balanced communication in the labs and other pilot workshops, it is obligatory to introduce a Code of Conduct (CoC) on seriousness, fairness, and transparency during the kick-off STECCI labs and the demo pilots with citizen science and co-creation. The CoC is presented at the beginning of the kick-off event and made available whenever new stakeholders participate in the labs. The STECCI consortium communicates when they are going to decide, how stakeholders' contributions will be considered and what kind of feedback will be given. It belongs to the key tasks of the lab moderators and facilitators to ensure that all participants are well informed about and respect the seriousness of the co-creation or citizen science process.

It is important that each participant has the same chance to have her or his say. Therefore, the process must be designed and implemented in a way that everybody – irrespective of age, sex, income – can participate equally. It is the moderators' and facilitators' task to ensure a proper implementation of this requirement.

STECCI consortium partners implementing SLs and CS activities take orientation on the following CoC principles:

- It must be ensured that all participants are provided with clear and barrier-free information. There are three stages of information: before the process, during the process and after the process.
- Pilot lead partners need to know their participants in advance, reminding them at the start of lab or citizen science workshop how they can benefit from taking part! To support the continuous commitment of participants, expectations and benefits must be highlighted to the potential STECCI lab participants:
- Expand your personal and professional network!

- Learn more about state-of-the-art safeguarding and preservation methods!
- Provide feedback in an early research and design phase for the cultural heritage valorisation in the STECCI project!
- Identify potential business opportunities in the field of tech/eco/social entrepreneurship!
- Peer learning – take advantage of the opportunity to exchange ideas with experts from different disciplines and sectors!
- Benefit from building a community of interest during the STECCI labs and become part of your local and regional social innovation strategy!

5. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This final chapter of D5.1 gives an outlook on the next steps in WP5 as T5.1 and T5.2 are closely interlinked. T5.1 prepares the framework and provides the basis for the implementation of STECCI Social Innovation labs and citizen science pilot activities.

In M8 of the project, a train-the-trainer workshop will brief lab and pilot teams on how to start the invitation process and to implement the kick-off events.

As described in the previous chapters, pilot leaders are invited to implement mandatory elements (World Café and storytelling workshop) under the STECCI umbrella as well as site-specific activities aligned with local and regional needs. To enable these steps, D5.1 provides a set of methods that can be tested and adapted during a period of 12 months in T5.2. The selection of these methods is the result of a preparatory research and co-design process of all consortium partners involved in this task. The methodology of STECCI Social Innovation labs and citizen science pilots takes advantage of preliminary findings, which will be further validated “on the ground”. Furthermore, the stakeholder mapping will be updated with the help of interviews and the discussion on needs implemented (World Café) during the kick-off events of the STECCI labs.

After the kick-off engagement and workshop events of each pilot is implemented, a cross-fertilisation workshop aims to enable the experience and knowledge transfer between consortium partners. Furthermore, this second internal workshop helps to calibrate further activities and to make visible how pilots can collaborate among each other to use synergies.

At least three engagement and workshop activities shall be implemented in the labs together with the communities until the end of T5.2, while in the Serbian pilot at least one, and in Germany at least two activities are foreseen. Due to the partly diverse character of pilots, more activities and outcomes can be desirable but are dependent on the goodwill and availability of lab participants and collaborating organisations.

At a later point of the project and after the series of T5.2 engagement events and workshops in each pilot, a feedback workshop will be organised together with consortium partners. This workshop is foreseen to

build evidence for the follow-up activities in WP5, WP4 as well as in WP6, and feeds into the D5.2 Report on the implementation of the stecci labs.

Fig. 18: Timeline of the co-creation process in T5.1 and T5.2

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7. APPENDIX

7.1. APPENDIX 1: SCOUT QUESTIONS & TEMPLATE FOR STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

PILOT / SITE [PARTNER ORGANISATION]

Interviewee / Interviewer / Minutes: [NAME OF PARTICIPANTS]

Date / Time: [DATE / TIME]

TOPICS	STATUS	LINKS etc.
GEOGRAPHIC AND HISTORIC CONTEXT AND CULTURAL DNA OF THE SITES	[DONE / WHAT IS MISSING]	[LINKS TO EMDESK & ZSI NEXTCLOUD]
DESCRIPTION OF PROBLEMS / ISSUES		
MAJOR OBJECTIVES		
COMPLEMENTARY OBJECTIVES		
VISION		
STAKEHOLDER / USERS		
USER		
MEMBERS OF THE MULTI-STAKEHOLDER FORUM		
KEY-KNOWLEDGE HOLDER		
LABMANAGER INTERN / EXTERN		
SCHEDULE ON PILOT / WORKSHOPS / SYNERGIES		
PLACES FOR WORKSHOPS / MEETINGS / EVENTS		
SOCIAL INCLUSIVENESS & DIVERSITY		
ACTIVITIES & OUTCOME OF COLLABORATION WITH CULTURAL & CREATIVE INDUSTRY AND CULTURAL TOURISM		
EXPECTED OUTCOME PEACE & DEMOCRACY INTERSECTION		
ACCESSIBILITY		

1. GEOGRAPHIC AND HISTORIC CONTEXT AND CULTURAL DNA OF [PILOT / SITE]: [NAME OF PILOT / SITE]

[Please specify the geographical and demographic characteristics of the sites]

Pilot case / Site	Population / Description	Main & complementary objectives
[NAME / LOCATION]	[POPULATION / DESCRIPTION]	[MAIN & COMPLEMENTARY OBJECTIVES]

QUESTIONS:

- How would you describe the (cultural, ecological, and socio-economic) DNA of the pilot neighbourhoods and region? [Further questions could be i.e.]
- What does stecci stand for in the neighbourhood and the region? Has the necropolis landmark character? OR: Is it neglected?
- What are the specifics of the neighbourhood/village/region? What are the potentials, needs or challenges and limitations there? (see also objectives)
- Is there anything else significant for the pilot and the neighbourhood?
- How is the land around necropolis used at presence? Is there a plan to re-define the use? Is the owner open to include needs and ideas of the community or core stakeholders?
- What are the most important regulations to take into consideration?
- Do assume historic knowledge about stecci in the community? Who is a key knowledge holder?

[INSERT INFORMATION HERE]

2. DESCRIPTION OF PROBLEMS / ISSUES

[Please include first bullet points, which will be checked and discussed during the first lab event]

QUESTIONS:

- What are the most pressing needs in the neighbourhood / village / region related to the STECCI objectives?
- What are the most urgent challenges?
- What is the status of your pilot case?

[INSERT INFORMATION HERE]

3. MAJOR OBJECTIVES

[Please define the complementary objectives e.g. sustainability, social responsibilities, effects on 3rd sector, etc.]

QUESTION:

- Please define the major objective briefly!

[INSERT INFORMATION HERE]

4. COMPLEMENTARY OBJECTIVES

[Please define the complementary objectives e.g. sustainability, social responsibilities, effects on 3rd sector, etc.]

QUESTION:

- Please draft 1 to 2 complementary objectives contributing to sustainable and social concepts and project activities on-site, in the community and neighbourhoods!

[INSERT INFORMATION HERE]

5. VISION

[Please concretise the vision and the advantages of your pilot / site]

QUESTION:

- Please briefly describe a vision for your pilot case - How does the best outcome and output look like?

[INSERT INFORMATION HERE]

6. STAKEHOLDER

[Please define and identify more stakeholder and user]

QUESTIONS:

- Who can benefit from the STECCI project (process and activities) and its results? How can they benefit?
- Whom to involve as participants from the beginning?
- Have you identified further gatekeepers already?
- What will / can core stakeholders bring in to enable or support the labs?
- How is the land around necropolis used at presence? Is there a plan to re-define the use?
Is the owner open to include needs and ideas of the community or core stakeholders?

[INSERT INFORMATION IN TABLE]

Stakeholders	Expected role	Engage-ment level	Expected benefit	Potential concerns

7. USER

[Please define the benefits that stakeholders will receive from the implementation of the project]

QUESTION:

- Who will be directly influenced by the STECCI project in your pilot case?

[INSERT INFORMATION IN TABLE]

Organisation	Contact person	E-Mail / Phone	General info	Benefit from the pilot/site

8. KEY-KNOWLEDGE HOLDER

[Please define the type of collaboration and the contact persons]

QUESTION:

- Does someone assume historic knowledge about stecci in the community? Who is a key knowledge holder?

[INSERT INFORMATION IN TABLE]

Key-knowledge holder	Organisation	Expertise	Contact

9. LAB MANAGER INTERN / EXTERN

[Please define the contact persons and their expertise]

QUESTION:

- Who can lead the social labs (e.g. as a lab manager)? Who will be a supporter (internal/external)?

INTERN: [NAME / EXPERTISE / CONTACT]

EXTERN: [NAME / EXPERTISE / CONTACT]

10. SCHEDULE ON PILOT / WORKSHOPS / SYNERGIES

[Please specify various events and possible synergies]

QUESTIONS:

- Are there events on-site / in the region, which could bring synergies to the co-creation processes or the social labs? In case of a YES, please define a first timeline.
- When are you able to kick-off labs? Are potential synergies with ongoing or other events and projects?
- Are you open to participatory elements in the lab such as participatory governance?

[INSERT INFORMATION IN TABLE]

Date of the 1st Social Lab Kick-off	Place of the 1st Social Lab Kick-off	Social Lab Manager	Other events taking place that can generate synergy

[FURTHER INFORMATION]

11. PLACES FOR WORKSHOPS / MEETING / EVENTS

[Please search for suitable locations]

QUESTION:

- Is there a space for workshops, meetings, events available? Please define asap.

[INSERT INFORMATION HERE]

12. SOCIAL INCLUSIVENESS & DIVERSITY

[Please insert information to Social Inclusiveness, diversity, and vulnerable groups]

QUESTION:

- Who shall be addressed when it comes to minorities or vulnerable groups? Have you been in contact already?

[INSERT INFORMATION IN TABLE]

Vulnerable/ marginalized groups	Mechanism for inclusion	Potential collaborations / synergies	Timetable

13. ACTIVITIES & OUTCOME OF COLLABORATION WITH CULTURAL & CREATIVE INDUSTRY AND CULTURAL TOURISM

[Please insert information to activities & outcome of collaboration]

[INSERT INFORMATION IN TABLE]

Sector	Organisation / Contact Person	Activity	Expected outcome

14. EXPECTED OUTCOME PEACE & DEMOCRACY INTERSECTION

[Please insert information to expected outcome of peace & democracy intersection]

[INSERT INFORMATION IN TABLE]

Intersection point / Location / Objects / Events	Description	Organisations / Contact persons	Expected outcome

15. ACCESSIBILITY

[Please research possible routes]

[INSERT INFORMATION HERE]

ACTION POINTS

[OPEN ISSUES / QUESTIONS FROM ZSI]